

Phytochemical screening of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. leaves from the area of Kaij of Beed District of Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:

Moringa oleifera has numerous benefits like nutritional as well as medicinal advantages. It contains essential amino acids, carotenoids in leaves, and nutritional supplements in cooking aspects. Leaves, and pods or drum sticks are having nutritional and medicinal properties. It has antioxidants, antibiotics and nutrients including vitamins and minerals. Now a days, leaves powder is used in various drinks for healthy life. In this paper, more emphasis is on its medicinal properties and phytochemical screening.

Introduction:

This single Genus *Moringa* belongs to family Marantaceae, Order Brassicales and species *oleifera*. It is small native tree of the sub-Himalayan regions of North west India which is now indigenous to many regions in Africa, Arabia, South East Asia, Pacific and Caribbean Islands and South America.

In Maharashtra, traditionally drum sticks are used in rasepi. It is also called as the miracle tree due to its healing abilities for some chronic diseases.

Medicinal uses of *Moringa* has been used to cure skin infections, anaemia, anxiety, asthma, blackheads, blood impurities, bronchitis, chest congestion, cholera. It is anti-inflammatory, antispasmodic, anti-hypertensive, antitumour, anti-oxidants, anti-pyretic, anti-ulcer, diuretic, lowering cholesterol, renal and anti-diabetic.

Utilization of *Moringa* Pods and Leaves:

Moringa was found to contain many essential nutrients, vitamins, minerals, amino acids. Its leaves consist of vitamins C, calcium, beta carotene, potassium and protein. It works as

an effective source of natural antioxidants. *Moringa* is having capacity to increase the period of food containing fats due to presence of flavanoids, ascorbic acid, carotenoids and phenolics.

Anti-inflammatory:

It is used in healing and huge amount of acute and chronic conditions.

In vitro and Vivo conditions it is recommended its effectiveness in treating inflammation.

Anti-diabetic:

Diabetes Mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder. Diabetic patients exhibit a stage of chronic hyperglycemia and glucose tolerance. It is also used for traditional treatment of diabetes. The nutritional and fatty acid profiles of the *Moringa* has highest anti-oxidant activity.

Material and Methods:

For this, leaves from *Moringa* leaves were collected from Kaij City area and nearby places. The collected leaves washed in water and allow to

dry for 5 to 6 days. After suitable drying of leaves, powder was prepared by grinding machine.

Extract Preparation:

1. Aqueous extract:

3 gm leaves powder + 30ml distilled water +15ml Methanol

2. Acetone extract:

3 gm leaves powder + 30 ml of Acetone

3. Chloroform extract:

3 gm of Moringa leaf powder + 30ml chloroform

Each extract was incubated for overnight and filtered by using Whatman No.1 filter paper in to flask. Filterates were collected by placing the flask in to water bath at 100 degree celcius. The resulting filterate were allowed to cool to room temperature. Then qualitative tests were

performed and phytochemicals were investigated by analysing different methods. These process following the rules of Evans 1997, Wagner 1993.

1. Test for Alkaloids:

Mayers Test:

2ml of each extract was mixed with 2.3 drops of Mayers reagent (1.36 gm mercuric iodide in 60 ml of water mix properly with 5 gm of Potassium iodide in 20ml of water) A white or creamy precipitate confirmed the test as positive.

Wagner's Test:

2 ml of each extract was mixed with 0.2 ml diluted HCl solution. Then 1 ml of Wagner's reagent was added. (1.27 g of Iodine and 2g potassium iodide along with 100ml distilled water.)

There was reddish brown precipitate that indicated the positive test.

Table Showing Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemicals	Name of Test	Aqueous extract	Aqueous Methanol extract	Acetone extract	Chloroform extract
Alkaloids	Mayers test	++	+	-	-
	Wagner's Test	++	+	-	-
Tannins	Feric Chloride Test	++	+	-	-
Saponins	Foam Test	+	+	-	++
Flavonoids	Lead acetate Test	+	+	-	-
Glycosides	Keller Killani Test	-	-	-	++

Flavonoids acts as an antioxidants and enhances the effect of Vitamin C. They are also known for their biological activity against liver toxins, carcinogens, viruses, and other microbes.

According to many researches, flavonoids basically acts as bacteria by inhibiting it's protein synthesis and also posses antimicrobial, and anti allergic and anti inflammatory properties. They are active in reducing high blood pressure.

Flavonoids is suggested as health promoting phytochemical for animal production because they are known for improving gut health.

2. Test for Tannins:

Feric Chloride Test:

2 ml of each extract mixed with few drops of 5 percent ferric chloride solution. Formation of blue colour indicated the presence of tannins.

3. Test for Saponins:

Foam Test:

5 ml of each extract shaken vigorously with 5 ml of distilled water in a test tube and warmed. Formation of stable foam indicated the test as positive.

4. Test for Flavonoids:

Lead acetic acid Test:

1 ml of each extract mixed with 1 ml of 10 percent lead acetate solution. Formation of yellow precipitate indicates the presence of flavanoids.

5. Test for Glycosides:

Keller -Killiani Test:

2 ml of each extract was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and 5% ferric chloride solution were added. The contents were heated and cooled, then transferred to a test tube containing 2 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. Pale green colour appear in the upper layer indicates the presence of glycoside.

Result and Discussion:

In this findings the presence of different biochemical constituents in moringa leaves extracts such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids and glycosides. Aqueous and aqueous methanol extract contained alkaloids, Tannins, saponins. Flavonoids and glycosides were as chloroform extracts contain glycosides. How your acetone extracts didn't contain any type of phytochemical phytochemical compounds. Saponins are used as an adjuvant in the production of vaccines. So due to presence of saponins the leaves of moringa acts as soap. This saponins have antioxidant properties anti-inflammatory and immuno stimulant properties.

Moringa leaves have alkaloids which are nitrogen containing naturally occurring compound which are having anti microbial properties. Due to this medicinal properties this leaves are used in the treatment of many diseases

like malaria, cold, cough hypertension, diabetes and cancer.

Conclusion:

This photochemical screening helps in possible preventive and curative properties of moringa leaves. But there is need to carry out more qualitative and quantitative pharmacological analysis of moringa leaves to prove the use of moringa as important medicine plant. There is more emphasis for screening of phytochemicals for various treatments of human diseases in rural areas of Kaji. There is more need to develop Ayush health centres for the treatment of diseases regarding medicinal plants like moringa. Our government should take more steps for the development of rural people by using these medicinal plants. Government should carry out programs like plantation of only medicinal plants in this area.

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